

New European Bauhaus

A digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus (NEB)

First Post-webinar Report

digiNEB.eu
digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus

Disclaimer

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The first webinar of digiNEB.eu project Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus (NEB) took place on December 12, 2022, with high-level representatives of the European Commission, digiNEB.eu project members, and experts in both digital and NEB ecosystems discussing the role of digital technologies to accomplish NEB's main pillars of sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion.

The event, moderated by **Silvana Muscella** (CEO, [Trust-IT Services](#)), who opened the webinar, invited attendees to join the NEB ecosystem by contributing to digiNEB.eu's offer. Potential initiatives include proposing solutions for the [Digital Toolkit](#), sharing a success story for the [Observatory](#), contributing to the eLearning catalogue, joining [Thematic Working Groups](#) and becoming [Early Adopters](#) of the NEB digital ecosystem.

The webinar's first part briefly introduced the New European Bauhaus, featuring two European Commission representatives, who outlined NEB's main principles and discussed digiNEB.eu potential contribution.

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The New European Bauhaus initiative: beautiful, sustainable, together - The EU Roadmap

The New European Bauhaus is the soul of the Green Deal, adding human values such as inclusion and beauty to the sustainability agenda

Alicja Magdalena Herbowska ([New European Bauhaus](#) acting Head of Unit, Joint Research Centre), outlined NEB's main principles and its current and future roadmap initiatives.

New European Bauhaus From concept to action

As she stated, the European Commission considers the New European Bauhaus as the “soul of the European Green Deal,” as it strives to add a human touch to the main principles of sustainable development with values such as inclusivity and beauty.

She also traced a general timeline on the construction of NEB, a co-creation process that began with Ursula von der Leyen’s speech in January 2021, and was followed by a period of debates within the European Commission and with other external stakeholders.

For this reason, aside from its three main values, NEB's approach relies on three main principles, negotiating geographical scale (global/local), participation and transdisciplinarity. These aim to enable thematic axes on the transformation paths such as reconnecting to nature, regaining a new sense of belonging, prioritising places and people in need, creating long-term lifecycle thinking in the industrial ecosystem.

Such an approach requires working at different levels, though a diversified package of programs in order to facilitate NEB's co-creation process. The most innovative element is the **NEB Lab** working together on projects that are of interest to people, with five commission-led projects and five community-led projects.

Commission-led projects aim to assess potential regulating barriers to NEB projects, understand how to accomplish innovative funding schemes to help smaller projects get funding and perform other philanthropic initiatives. Another tool is the labelling strategy to help other projects to join the NEB ecosystem. The last pillar of this package focuses on potential actions to rebuild Ukraine adopting NEB's principles.

The community-led package includes other initiatives such as [NEB Goes South](#), the [New European Bauhaus of the Mountains](#), [Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus](#) and many more currently in the pipeline.

All these initiatives are regulated by the **NEB Compass**, a guiding framework for decision makers wishing to apply NEB principles and criteria to their activities and projects through a rating system attributing score levels from one to three on NEB principles.

New European Bauhaus Compass

These frameworks are informed and regulated by a pool of experts known as the High Level Round Table, and National Contact Points who provide strategic guidelines and coordinate NEB efforts locally. Public authorities and NGOs can also be part of the NEB ecosystem by becoming official [NEB friends](#) and join NEB's initiatives and events, as well as facilitating public participation in NEB-organised events.

NEB Community

- 561 Official Partners**
non political and non-for profit organisations
- 19 Members of the High-Level Round Table**
practitioners in different fields relevant to NEB
- 99 NEB Prize winners & finalists**
promoters of inspiring projects illustrating the NEB triangle of values
- 27 National Contact Points**
public authorities coordinating national efforts to implement the initiative
- 77 Friends**
companies and public authorities
 - > NEB dedicated calls' beneficiaries
 - > NEB Team & other relevant EC colleagues

Eddy Hartog ([European Commission](#) DG Connect, Head of Unit Technologies for Smart Communities), reinforced some points raised by Alicja Magdalena Herbowska, explaining how digiNEB.eu can play a key role in contributing to local digital transformations (e.g. local dataspaces and digital twins), knitting together key strategic points on EC's agenda: **green transformation and digital technologies**.

The role of the digital ecosystem in the construction industry

The digitalisation of the construction sector tangibly took off in the last decade with many large-scale implementations based on digital tools for planning, design, construction, and operations for facilities

The webinar's second part prioritised the role of the digital ecosystem in the construction industry, featuring **Jesús Angel García Sánchez** (of the [ECTP](#) Executive Board on Digital Built Environment). Jesús remarked on the importance of the built environment sector, representing 9% of Europe's total GDP. He focused particularly on the digitalisation of the sector, discussing different applications, such as smart metre deployment, IT-based energy solutions, digital twins for scenario forecasting and buildings fine-tuning, building retrofit, organisation of worksites, solutions for elderly people's comfort. In this context, digital twins are relevant not only for operational reasons but also for other activities such as meteorological predictions, material testing and building operations.

Overall, digitalisation is essential for industrialisation processes to test and check different scenarios. Eventually these digital solutions will be shared among people for different purposes. For this reason the Digital Built Environment Committee was created, gathering the best practices for other sectors in order to reuse these technologies to support and ensure the penetration of cutting-edge technologies in the construction sector. In this context, it is essential to provide guidelines for user applications, which are at the core of the ECTP Committee on Digital Built Environment.

User stories across

Many of the ideas that DUVED embodies clearly embody NEB principles and digiNEB.eu's agenda

The third part of the webinar focused more specifically on digiNEB.eu, with some examples of user stories across Europe. The first speaker, digiNEB.eu's partner **Roberto Cavallo** (Council member of [European Association for Architectural Education EAAE](#)), illustrated the project's Early Adopters campaign looking for people and best practices making use of digital solutions in order to contribute to NEB.

Roberto also highlighted the main benefits of becoming an Early Adopter:

- sharing and transferring best practices of utilising digital solutions in your NEB-related projects;
- identifying gaps in the NEB digital ecosystem and helping find solutions to address them;
- gaining visibility at local and/or international events;

He also introduced the first solution, the Duvet project, representing digiNEB.eu

Are you an adopter of digital solutions in the NEB context?

**Visit our website
and join our community**

Jan Åman (Senior Researcher at [Industry Commons Foundation](#)) described more in-depth the Duved project. Duved is a small village in the North of Sweden, which became a litmus test to understand some of the world's challenges and try potential planning solutions. The project's main aim is to overcome the centralised and top-down industrial factory model, promoting the idea of an ecosystem addressing key global (climate change, war) and local challenges, update ideas of democracy, systems for housing, food waste, smart mobility, knowledge-production, artisanal housing and local crafts.

The village domain provided an ideal scenario to address these challenges, to redefine the democracy system through participatory systems of discussion and debates. About 40% of the villagers attended the meetings to become part of their neighbourhood's decision-making process aimed at devising innovative solutions without creating side effects such as affordability issues and gentrification.

In this innovation context, the rural area thus became an asset due to lower prices, more agile bureaucracy and easier decision-making processes. Specifically, Duved's digital solution was based on creating a digital space to communicate results from villagers' meetings to other actors such as policy-makers using aerial photography linked to phones and digital meetings which kept going on all the time. This allowed politicians to communicate the results of their decisions to the villagers, involving different groups in decision-making processes and training multiple social layers at using this tool.

Panel Discussion - Present and future of digital solutions for NEB

A panel discussion moderated by **Silvana Muscella** followed where experts in the NEB field were invited to share their viewpoints. Climate-neutral cities and digitalisation practices were the two main topics.

1st Round

NEB digital solutions facilitating and accelerating the transition to climate-neutral cities

Michela Magas (Chair at [Industry Commons Foundation](#) and member of the [NEB High-level roundtable](#)) highlighted how the NEB community can facilitate cultural shifts toward more sustainable practices and propel behavioural transformations. As to digital solutions, NEB principles can safeguard the social dimension of technology, immersing it into culture. This would allow a new approach to engaging with emerging technologies and new market opportunities, creating a win-win situation for users and technology providers.

Jan Aman complemented by remarking on the importance of scaling up digital solutions to have a direct use in dialogue with adopters from different social layers.

Ruth Schagemann (President of the [Architects' Council of Europe](#), ACE), contextualised the question to the field of architecture, where NEB acts as a blueprint for the transformation of the built environment into a better version of itself, according to important societal and environmental values. Moreover, NEB explores new aesthetic frontiers pushing forward scenario simulations that were not possible before, developing tools to improve the whole design process. In this context, open-source tools are especially critical to propel innovation processes and shared knowledge practices.

**2nd
Round:**

Practical examples on how digitalisation practices can contribute to the application of NEB principles.

Ruth Schagemann mentioned artificial intelligence as a significant digital innovation for architects, due to its different potential applications in the architectural domain, especially gathering different types of datasets which could inform best practices. This is still a new field but there could be new developments within a very short period of time.

Michela Magas complemented by mentioning that one of the most important technologies for achieving the Green Deal is closed-loop material lifecycle management. This requires progress in related data standardisation and interoperability across domains. Inclusion and aesthetics are often not considered by digital solution providers. There are many examples of how digital technologies can help people with limited abilities to develop their own business and accomplish tangible results, or can create affordances to integrate heterogeneous communities in the job market. The High Level Round Table research suggests that beauty emanates out of a sense of community. This can lead to complete new levels of virtuosity, which becomes the ultimate expression of beauty and can meaningfully contribute to societal transformations.

Jesús Angel García Sánchez highlighted that since the construction sector uses many raw materials and resources it is certainly the main sector to test these digital technologies in order to improve their feasibility. For example, new technological simulators combining BIM and digital twins are great tools for integrated life-cycle sustainability assessment.

Alicja Magdalena Herbowska mentioned the large number of examples within the NEB ecosystem where inclusion creates beauty and allows meaningful interactions between different human groups and other species, for different aims: from heritage protection, to interaction in urban spaces.

The webinar hosted 149 registrants from 32 countries, representing a diversified set of professionals. Below is an infographic detailing these figures.

About digiNEB.eu and the New European Bauhaus

digiNEB.eu
digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus

The New European Bauhaus (NEB) is a creative and transdisciplinary initiative to connect the European Green Deal to people's daily lives and living spaces. Building on its three inseparable values of sustainability, aesthetics and inclusivity, NEB calls on all Europeans to imagine and build together a sustainable and inclusive future, bringing together different social layers (citizens, experts, businesses and institutions).

digiNEB.eu is supporting the NEB community by developing a digital ecosystem for NEB sustainable and inclusive living spaces, which is composed of:

- **Digital Toolkit:** a catalogue with over 200 digital solutions for the NEB ecosystem;
- **Observatory:** a collection of 500 EU-funded initiatives and success stories to raise awareness towards NEB programmes and the benefits of digital solutions, and encourage collaborations;
- **eLearning catalogue:** a collaborative online set of courses and training materials aimed at stimulating knowledge and sharing best practices.

Apply to our services to contribute to shaping more sustainable, inclusive and beautiful living spaces:

- [Visit the Digital Toolkit, discover available solutions and add new ones](#)
- [Explore the Observatory and share digital and NEB-related success stories](#)
- [Join our community of digiNEB.eu Early Adopters](#)
- [Contribute to our TWG open discussions](#)

Follow the New European Bauhaus digital journey by visiting the related websites and follow the social media channels to keep updated on the latest news and developments:

New European Bauhaus

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